

HyPVCar-CM_Data_Management_Plan.xml

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) contains the datasets produced through the **Hybrid Structures for Integration of Photovoltaic Cells in Car Bodies** project (HyPVCar-CM), which seeks to establish the basis for integrating photovoltaic (PV) cells into steel and aluminium structures for automotive applications.

The HyPVCar-CM aims to simulate, develop, and validate hybrid multilayer structures for integrating silicon PV cells into metallic automotive body parts. The project investigates multilayer hybrid structures designed to meet requirements for aesthetics, durability, encapsulation, electrical insulation, manufacturability, mechanical performance, and cost-effectiveness. As a result, flat and curved samples will be fabricated and characterized using macro- and microscale testing to assess tensile behaviour, fatigue, impact resistance, corrosion, and electrical performance after integration.

Following the FAIR principles and the Open Science practices adopted by the project, the DMP has been developed using the ARGOS platform. All datasets and related research outputs will be managed to ensure long-term accessibility and reuse. In this context, an official Zenodo community has been established to guarantee open access, preservation, and discoverability: [HyPVCar-CM community](#).

This project has been funded through the R&D Activities Program for Research Groups in the Synergistic modality, under reference SYG-2024/ECO-1016 and acronym HyPVCar-CM, awarded by the Community of Madrid through the Directorate-General for Research and Technological Innovation under Order 5022/2025, dated October 19.

Funder

COMUNIDAD DE MADRID

Grant

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1. Main Info

Title of DMP: HyPVCar-CM_Data_Management_Plan.xml

Description: This Data Management Plan (DMP) defines the procedures for managing the outputs generated in the *Hybrid Structures for Integration of Photovoltaic Cells in Car Bodies* project (HyPVCar-CM). This document has been developed in alignment with **FAIR principles** and **Open Science practices**, ensuring that all project data remains findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

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Organizations:

The Synergy call fosters collaboration between complementary research teams to advance in disruptive projects at the frontier of knowledge. Our project combines photovoltaics and material science to develop sustainable solar solutions for the mobility sector.

- 1- Integration of Systems and Instruments (ISI) from INSTITUTO DE ENERGÍA SOLAR (UPM).
- 2- Physical Simulation and Characterization (PS-IMDEA) from FUNDACIÓN IMDEA MATERIALES.

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: COMUNIDAD DE MADRID

Grants: SYG-2024/ECO-1016

Project: Hybrid Structures for Integration of Photovoltaic Cells in Car Bodies (HyPVCar-CM)

3. License

License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Template: RSU DMP Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose is to generate mechanical, microstructural, electrical, and simulation datasets to characterize hybrid multilayer structures for PV solar integration into metallic car body parts. These data support the design, validation, modelling, and reliability assessment of Vehicle-Integrated Photovoltaics (VIPV).

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Our project combines materials science, mechanical engineering, and PV technology, producing data valuable to researchers in PV, material science, automotive engineering, mechanical modelling, and manufacturing, as well as to industrial partners, VIPV developers, and standardization bodies.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data (mechanical testing, fatigue, impact, corrosion)
- Simulation data (numerical models, and the scripts used for analysis or validation)
- Associated documentation (experimental protocol, lab notes, methodological process, and README file)
- Technical images

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- Text and structured formats: *TXT, CSV, XLS, ODS, ODK, JSON, XML*
- Documentation formats: *PDF, HTML, ODT*
- Image and microstructural data formats: *TIFF, PNG*
- Statistical formats: *SAV*

1.2.3 Are you re-using this dataset?

All datasets will be newly generated at this stage. If external datasets are reused, compliance with the original license and citation will be ensured.

1.3 FAIR Compliance

1.3.1 Findable

All outputs will be deposited in Zenodo, which will automatically assign a DOI. Metadata will follow the DataCite scheme, including title, authors, affiliations, keywords, description, versioning and funding information. Clear keywords will ensure the findability of all datasets.

1.3.2 Accessible

Data and associated metadata will be openly accessible through the HyPVCAR-CM Zenodo community without embargo. Zenodo provides persistent identifiers, stable URLs, and long-term preservation. Metadata will remain accessible even if datasets require updates, ensuring FAIR compliance.

1.3.3 Interoperable

It will be ensured through open and widely supported data formats (CSV, JSON, TIFF, PDF). Although no specific ontology exists for PV multilayer hybrid structures, mechanical testing or simulation workflows, the consortium promotes an internal vocabulary to ensure consistency. Metadata standards (DataCite / Dublin Core) also support interoperability.

1.3.4 Reusable

Data will be licensed under CC-BY 4.0, which allows broad reuse providing proper author attributions. All datasets will include supporting documentation to ensure reproducibility, such as README files, codebooks, or methodology descriptions. Experimental conditions, processing parameters, and analysis methods will be recorded to ensure that data is fully understandable and reusable by third parties.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data? If yes, will you use any metadata standard?

Yes. The datasets will be deposited in Zenodo, which applies the DataCite Metadata Standard and ensures rich standardized metadata and FAIR compliance. The following metadata will be incorporated for dataset deposit:

- Resource type: dataset, software, report, presentation, image, etc.
- Title: descriptive and unique.
- Authors: affiliation and ORCID number.
- Description: origin, methods, instrumentation, software, or parameters.
- Keywords: relevant technical terms.
- DOI: if not provided, it is automatically assigned by Zenodo.
- Funding information: including project reference (SYG-2024/ECO-1016), acronym (HyPVCAR-CM), and funded by the Sinergicos Call by Comunidad de Madrid.
- Communities: HyPVCAR-CM community.
- Access rights: supported by CC-BY 4.0.
- Version: version number.

- Related identifiers: include links to associated publications, software, or datasets.
- Format: file formats.
- Date: creation or publication date.
- Language: English.

2.1.3 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.4 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you document the dataset?

Yes, where necessary, the datasets will be accompanied by appropriate documentation by Codebook files, ReadMe files, laboratory notebooks, experimental protocols, or methodology descriptions.

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The datasets can be accessed using standard spreadsheet, image-viewing, or scientific computing tools (Excel, LibreOffice, Python/MATLAB, etc.).

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

Yes

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, metadata, documentation and code be made accessible through a repository?

Yes, an official Zenodo community guarantees open access at: [HyPVCar-CM community](#).

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0).

2.3.3 What type of access will the dataset have (choose one)?

Open (anyone can access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to this data?

No embargo is considered, so the data will be made available at the earliest possible stage.

2.3.5 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data, and who acts as the data controller?

INSTITUTO DE ENERGÍA SOLAR and FUNDACIÓN IMDEA MATERIALES act as data controllers, since each of them generates, processes, and manages different parts of the datasets.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and DMP maintenance?

Víctor Bellón (IES UPM) will act as Data Manager, coordinating data documentation, quality assurance, processing workflows, and updates of the initial DMP version. Email address: victor.bellon@upm.es

3.1.3 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors- researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other people who will work with the data for this study)?

The data will be collected and processed by researchers, lab technicians, assistants, and other people affiliated with the UPM and IMDEA Materiales.

3.1.4 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes. The consortium (UPM–IMDEA Materials) has established data quality assurance processes to ensure accuracy, consistency, and reproducibility of all datasets generated.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

Access is limited to authorized project members. Servers include frequent backup, recovery, and secure transference mechanisms provided by each institution.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

Data will be stored on secure institutional servers for at least five years after completion, following institutional data policies.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your repository is appropriate for long-term preservation and curation?

Yes. Zenodo provides long term preservation, DOI assignment, metadata standards, and is maintained by OpenAIRE, ensuring sustainability and compliance with FAIR principles.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

No ethical or legal issues apply. The project does not involve human subjects or personal data, so no informed consent is required. All data are technical and relate only to materials, mechanical, electrical, and simulation results. Data will be processed and accessed following institutional security procedures and applicable national regulations.